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ABSTRACT

Introduction: A 7-year-old girl presented with 2-month history of continuous coughing; despite detailed anamnesis and physical examination, no organic cause was found. The cough was barking, explosive, unproductive, and was reported not to be during sleep. As a result of detailed anamnesis, physical examination and auxiliary laboratory tests, no organic pathology was detected.

Case Presentation: Considering the provisional diagnosis of a psychogenic cough, she was advised for psychiatry consultation. After psychiatric evaluation, selective mutism and anxiety disorder were detected. She was initially treated with behavioral therapy. Fluoxetine was added to her treatment because she did not show the expected progress with treatment.

Discussion: There was a significant improvement in her symptoms at 1-month follow-up. Improvement continued at subsequent follow-ups.

Conclusion: This case emphasizes the importance of considering psychogenic cough in patients with chronic cough. It also demonstrates the necessity of identifying and treating comorbid psychiatric problems in the management of psychogenic cough.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Chronic cough, Diagnosis of exclusion, Psychogenic cough

INTRODUCTION

Psychogenic cough, a type of chronic cough, is a diagnosis of exclusion that must be determined after careful and comprehensive evaluation (Irwin, Glomb, & Chang, 2006). In psychogenic cough, no organic cause can be determined, the cough is barking and non-productive. It is not seen during sleep or when the person's attention is elsewhere. The cough increases in intensity in the presence of other people or when the patient realizes being observed. The cough is not suppressed by any medication and does not worsen with laughing, crying, exertion, etc (Pierce & Watson, 1998).

CASE PRESENTATION

A seven-year-old girl was admitted with a cough that had been ongoing for 2 months. It was learned that the cough was dry and usually did not occur while sleeping. There was no other complaint such as fever, sore throat, etc. in her history. Her occasional coughs in the outpatient clinic were barking. When talking to the patient, it was observed that her cough had stopped, and her eyes remained open during coughing. Her percentiles were within the age-appropriate range. Her physical examination was normal. Infection parameters were negative in blood tests, and her chest X-ray was normal. A child psychiatry evaluation was requested with a preliminary diagnosis of psychogenic cough in the patient. After psychiatric evaluation, selective mutism and anxiety disorder were detected. Initially, behavioral therapy was applied. Since she did not show the expected progress with the treatment, fluoxetine was added to her treatment. There was a significant improvement in her symptoms at 1-month follow-up. Improvement continued in subsequent follow-ups and her complaint resolved within 2.5 months.

DISCUSSION

The prevalence of psychogenic cough is a matter of debate in the literature, and it is reported to be seen in 3-10% of children with chronic cough (Irwin, Glomb, & Chang, 2006). The diagnosis of psychogenic cough, which is more common in girls, is a diagnosis of exclusion (Irwin et al., 1998). Psychogenic cough has its own characteristics; it is noisy, explosive and does not produce phlegm. It increases when attention is directed to the person, is unresponsive to multiple drug therapy, occurs only when awake and disappears in the absence of the parent or doctor (Braman, 2006). In our case, the cough of our seven-year old girl was harsh, hard and dry and was absent during sleep.

It has been reported in the literature that children with psychogenic cough may have an underlying psychiatric disorder, the most common being conversion disorder (21.9%) and mixed anxiety and depressive disorder (12.2%) (Bhatia, Chandra, & Vaid, 2002). Our case was also diagnosed with selective mutism and anxiety disorder after child psychiatry evaluation. There is no approved medication for the treatment of psychogenic cough. The most commonly recommended treatment methods in these cases are suggestion therapy, hypnosis, reassurance and counseling. Studies have shown that selective serotonin reuptake inhibitors are effective in the presence of comorbid anxiety disorders (Jakati, Naskar, & Khanna, 2017). In our case, a combined treatment approach with suggestion and SSRI was applied and a response was obtained.

In children presenting with chronic cough, a good analysis of the cough character, detailed anamnesis and physical examination are extremely helpful in the diagnosis of psychogenic cough. In addition, child psychiatry evaluation is necessary for common psychosocial problems such as anxiety, depression and family problems in these patients.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in psychogenic cough, a good understanding of the cough characteristics, detailed physical examination and follow-up are essential for diagnosis. In addition, child psychiatry evaluation is required to determine the psychiatric problems that may accompany psychogenic cough and to provide an appropriate treatment approach.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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